

Functional variation of minimum spouting velocity with static bed height in conical spouted beds

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ABSTRACT

Static height (H_0) is a key parameter in spouted bed as it is dictated by the amount of solids. Knowledge of minimum spouting velocity (u_{ms}) is a pre-requisite for optimal spouting condition for the loaded bed. Although a linear variation of u_{ms} with H_0 has been reported, this is not strictly true. Runs were performed using particles having a wide range of densities (2500–16000 kg/m³) and sizes (570–2440 μm). u_{ms} was measured for a wide range of H_0 values from those in the conical zone to those having a double height in the upper cylindrical one. Expressing $u_{ms} \propto H_0^\alpha$, with α being the exponent of the bed height, this exponent has a high dependency (~0.5–2.0) on the particle features, and therefore on the bed regime. This will help to rightfully choose the value of α for a given set of particles processed in conical spouted beds with different H_0 .

1. Introduction

Spouted Bed (SB) is among the most efficient solid-fluid contactors, as is versatile for unit operations and reactions, especially those involving heavy (typically $\rho_p > 5 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and big size particles ($d_p > 0.5 \text{ mm}$) (Epstein and Grace, 1997). Industrially deployed SBs are well known for efficient conversion of biomass, waste plastic and waste tyres into synthetic gas or green hydrogen (Orozco et al., 2023; Cortazar et al., 2019; Lopez et al., 2017; Niksiar et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2023; Lopez et al., 2009), as well as drying of food grains or nuts (Sukunza et al., 2022, 2021; Pablos et al., 2019; Souza et al., 2023; Brito et al., 2019), coating over pharmaceutical products or nuclear fuel or functional materials (Guo et al., 2023; Al-Juwaya et al., 2023; Mollick et al., 2011; Sathiyamoorthy et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2012; López-Honorato et al., 2008; Mathur and Gishler, 1955; Olazar et al., 1994; Mollick et al., 2015; Abyzov, 2022; Raman et al., 2022a, 2022b; Mollick et al., 2020, 2019, 2018; Mollick and Sathiyamoorthy, 2012).

The minimum spouting velocity, u_{ms} , is the velocity measured at the inlet orifice below the bed, required to maintain a sustainable spout zone in a spouted bed. Thus, maintaining the operating fluid velocity above u_{ms} is a mandatory for the rightful process outcomes. In many of the

spouted bed processes, d_p and ρ_p change with time. This is the case during drying, coating (depending on the density of the coated materials) or during the reactions of solid particles in biomass pyrolysis (Sukunza et al., 2022, 2021; Pablos et al., 2019; Mollick et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2012; López-Honorato et al., 2008). At times, static bed height can also be changed if the size of the particles changes during the process. Therefore, simultaneous changes in H_0 , d_p and ρ_p would be expected to change the u_{ms} .

In the past, many attempts have been made to correlate u_{ms} with H_0 , d_p and ρ_p , which can help to calculate an optimum operating spouting gas velocity in a SB (Mathur and Gishler, 1955; Olazar et al., 1994; Abdelrazek, 1969; Choi and Meisen, 1992; Kmiec, 1983; Kmiec, 1984). However, the influence of H_0 on u_{ms} has been reported differently for different sets of SB systems and particle properties (Tsvik et al.; Rocha et al., 1995; Zhou and Bruns, 2012; Golshan et al., 2019; Mollick et al., 2024). Expressing u_{ms} as $u_{ms} \propto H_0^\alpha$, where α is the exponent of the static bed height, the values reported for this exponent range from 0.5 to close to 2.0. Table 1 shows a summary of the previous findings by researchers.

As can be seen in Table 1, Mathur & Gishler had used highly non spherical particles with $d_p = 0.5\text{--}3.1 \text{ mm}$ and $\rho_p = 1.1\text{--}2.67 \text{ g/cc}$ and reported the value of α is 0.5 when the H_0 was maintained above the

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Table 1
Values of the exponent (α) over H_0 from the correlations reported in the past.

Serial No.	Authors and references	α	Range of parameters	Remarks
1	Mathur & Gishler, 1955	0.5	No variation in D_c , $\gamma_c = 85^\circ$, particles are highly non spherical with $d_p = 0.5$ – 3.1 mm and $\rho_p = 1.1$ – 2.67 g/cc (seeds, wheat, peas)	$H_0 > H_c$
2	Tsvik et al., 1967	1.24	Range of H_0 : 100–500 mm, $d_p = 1.5$ – 4.0 mm and $\rho_p = 1.65$ – 1.7 g/cc (fertilizer)	$H_0 < H_c$
3	Abdelrazek, 1969	0.5	Range of H_0 : 50–300 mm with range of D_c : 50–100 mm, $d_p = 1.5$ – 4.0 mm and $\rho_p = 1.65$ – 1.7 g/cc (glass and steel spheres)	$H_0 > H_c$
4	Kmiec et al., 1977	1.535	Range of H_0 : 500–600 mm with range of D_c : 88–180 mm, $\gamma_c = 24.1$ & 30° , $d_p = 0.87$ – 6.17 mm and $\rho_p = 1.29$ – 2.99 g/cc (sand, glass, silica gel)	$H_0 > H_c$
5	Kmiec et al., 1983	1.757	Range of H_0 : 50–510 mm with range of D_c : 88–900 mm, $d_p = 0.87$ – 3.7 mm and $\rho_p = 0.85$ – 2.99 g/cc (rape seed, Teflon, sand)	$H_0 < H_c$
6	Choi & Meisen, 1992	1.08	Range of H_0 : 240–530 mm with a fixed D_c : 240 mm, $d_p = 2.16$ – 2.8 mm and $\rho_p = 1.05$ – 1.09 g/cc (polystyrene, PE)	$H_0 > H_c$
7	Olazar et al., 1994	0.5	Range of H_0 : 160–450 mm with a fixed D_c : 150 mm, $d_p = 1$ – 8 mm and $\rho_p = 1.25$ – 2.42 g/cc (glass, rice, polystyrene)	$H_0 > H_c$
8	Rocha et al., 1995	1	Range of H_0 : 54.1–280 mm with range of D_c : 50–570 mm, $d_p = 6.49$ mm and $\rho_p = 1.02$ g/cc (inert tablets)	$H_0 < H_c$
9	Zhou et al., 2012	1.59	Range of H_0 : 30–50 mm with a fixed D_c : 50 mm, $d_p = 0.3$ – 0.65 mm and $\rho_p = 5.89$ g/cc (Zirconia)	$H_0 < H_c$
10	Golshan et al., 2018	1.3212	Range of H_0 : 40–144 mm with range of D_c : 150–250 mm, $d_p = 0.5$ – 2.0 mm and $\rho_p = 2.46$ – 6.05 g/cc (Glass, Alumina, Zirconia)	$H_0 < H_c$

conical zone (Mathur and Gishler, 1955). Similar value of $\alpha = 0.5$ was reported by Olazar et al. and Abdelrazek (Olazar et al., 1994; Abdelrazek, 1969), even though they had used spherical particles of similar range in size and density as used by Mathur & Gishler. Interesting fact is that, all of them studied the u_{ms} for the static bed height which is above the conical zone.

In contrary, Choi & Meisen and Kmiec et al., studied the u_{ms} using the bed height above the conical zone, but they have reported the value of α is 1.08 & 1.53, respectively (Choi and Meisen, 1992; Kmiec, 1983). In the other work, Kmiec et al. further reported the value of α is 1.75 when H_0 was maintained within the conical zone (Kmiec, 1984). However, the interesting fact is that they have reported the increased value of α from 1.53 to 1.75 when the bed height was above the conical zone and within the conical zone respectively.

On the other hand, those who have studied the u_{ms} within the conical zone (Kmiec, 1984; Tsvik et al.; Rocha et al., 1995; Zhou and Bruns, 2012; Golshan et al., 2019) have reported the value of α is equal or higher than unity (≥ 1). However, if it is noticed carefully, the value of α is close to 1.5 if the ρ_p is in a range of 3–6 g/cc (Kmiec, 1984; Tsvik et al.; Rocha et al., 1995; Zhou and Bruns, 2012; Golshan et al., 2019).

To our knowledge, the underline reason for such a large variation has never been reported in addressing all the relevant issues pertain to it.

Therefore, in the present work, we re-examine the u_{ms} with a large variation of particle size and density to report a comprehensive pattern of dependency of the α value on the H_0 for both, within and above the conical zones.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material

Three types of solid particles have been used in this study. They were chosen in such a way that the range of average ρ_p is wide. Table 2 shows the properties of the solid particles used. Industrial grade argon was used as the spouting gas for all the experiments.

2.2. Geometry

Schematic of a typical SB apparatus is shown in Fig. 1 with dimensions. The apparatus is made of glass with gas inlet nozzle as a separate glass tube. Glass apparatus was chosen for the transparency to observe particle movement hence identifying the correct u_{ms} .

2.3. Method

Systematic experiments were performed using three different particles and argon as the spouting gas. Argon was chosen as the spouting gas as it inert in nature and has higher density and viscosity than air. Higher in density and viscosity in argon helps attaining spouting (Mollick et al., 2019) (especially for the high density tungsten carbide particles) at a relatively low gas flow rate compared to air or nitrogen. The measured minimum spouting velocities correspond to the pre-decided static bed height (H_0), with the solid bed being charged from the top of the apparatus every time in each experiment. Argon was supplied from the commercial grade argon gas cylinder with an outlet pressure of 2 bar. Minimum spouting flow rate was measured in each experiments and u_{ms} was calculated based on the inlet orifice diameter (D_0).

3. Results and discussion

The u_{ms} was determined at different H_0 for the case of zirconium oxide particles of average $d_p = 730$ μm and density (ρ_p) = 6200 kg/m^3 . The range of H_0 has been considered from 0.015 to 0.18 m (within and above the conical zone). It is observed that u_{ms} increases with H_0 as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, u_{ms} is defined as a function of H_0 in the following form:

$$u_{ms} \propto H_0^\alpha \quad (1)$$

where, ' α ' is the exponent over H_0 .

3.1. Dependency of α on H_0

In order to determine the value of α , logarithmic variation of H_0 and u_{ms} is plotted and shown in Fig. 3. Interestingly, the value of α is found to vary with H_0 when an average slope has been considered for the incremental sets of data points for different H_0 studied here. The value of α (slope) is found to decrease constantly with the increase in H_0 . In other

Table 2
Properties of the particles.

Sl. No.	Material	Density, kg/m^3	Average size, μm
1	Glass bead	2500	2440
2	Zirconium oxide	6200	570 730 890 1950
3	Tungsten carbide	16000	1880

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of a Spouted Bed (SB) apparatus, (b) actual glass made apparatus, gas inlet nozzle assembly and a glimpse of visible spouting condition.

Fig. 2. Variation of u_{ms} with H_0 . ($d_p = 730 \mu\text{m}$ & $\rho_p = 6200 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

Fig. 3. Variation of α with H_0 ($d_p = 730 \mu\text{m}$ & $\rho_p = 6200 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

words, the rate of change of u_{ms} with H_0 is decreasing with increasing H_0 , as evidence by the systematic decrease in the value of α . The u_{ms} was determined starting from an H_0 value of one fourth the H_c to triple the H_c (double of height above the conical section). The value of α is found to be very high (~ 2) when $H_0 \ll H_c$, whereas it becomes close to unity (~ 1) when $H_0 \sim H_c$. A further increase in H_0 makes the slope less than unity and steadily decreasing with H_0 . This may be explained because when H_0 is relatively low, the particulate bed material is more interactive with the inlet gas, i.e., without particles steadily being locked in the bulk (annulus region) of the bed. In other words, when H_0 is relatively high, a lower fraction of the inlet gas percolates into the annulus, and therefore bed turbulence (solid circulation) in the annulus is lower, which involves a lower contribution of the inlet flow rate to spouting. Researchers in the past has shown similar trends reporting higher dependency of H_0 on u_{ms} within the conical zone and much lower dependency above the conical zone (see Table 1). Our findings agree well with previously reported values of the α for different regimes of the bed height studied by different researchers (Kmiec, 1984; Tsvik et al.; Rocha et al., 1995; Zhou and Bruns, 2012; Golshan et al., 2019; Mollick et al., 2024).

It can also be noted that the value of α reported bed Mathur & Gishler (1955) is 0.5 for the cone angle (γ_c) 85° , which corresponds to a very shallow bed. On the other hand, Kmiec et al. (1977) observed the value of α is 1.53 for a SB having very steep cone angle of $24\text{--}30^\circ$. The value of α is 1.53 with such a lower cone angle, and when the bed materials remain inside the conical zone, which is consistent with our experimental findings. Hence, it can be generally stated that the value of α is higher for lower γ_c and vice-versa.

3.2. Dependency of α on ρ_p

It is quite intuitive that a bed consisting of high-density particles would exert more downward gravitational force, and therefore require higher inlet flow rates for spouting. In order to check this fact, three different types of particulate beds have been used in the study having $\rho_p = 2500, 6200$ & 16000 kg/m^3 . Although the average d_p was not the same, we tried to choose those with d_p as close as possible to avoid the effect of the size. Average d_p values were $2440, 1950$ & $1880 \mu\text{m}$, respectively (see Table 2). The u_{ms} values have been determined for heights within and above the conical zone. The plot in Fig. 5 shows the variation of α with ρ_p . The value of α is found to increase with ρ_p , which is consistent with the earlier findings by other researchers listed in Table 1. Almost all the previous researchers reported higher values of α for higher ρ_p and vice-versa.

Fig. 4. Variation of α with ρ_p .

Fig. 5. Variation of α with d_p ($\rho_p = 6200 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

3.3. Dependency of α on d_p

Four different d_p were chosen to ascertain the effect of d_p on α and the results are shown in Fig. 5. The value of α with the d_p is seen to decrease linearly, which means that the larger the size of the particle the lower its effect on H_0 and vice-versa. This may be explained because bed permeability increases when d_p is increased, but the contact surface area for gas-solid and solid-solid decreases (this happens because surface area to volume ratio is smaller when particle size is increased, and vice versa), leading to a lesser interaction with the gas stream.

4. Conclusions

In the present work, u_{ms} is found to increase with H_0 for the all experiments conducted within the experimental conditions reported here. However, if we can express u_{ms} as a function of H_0 with α as an exponent over the H_0 , α is found to depend on H_0 , ρ_p and d_p . Typically, the value of α is slightly higher than unity when the bed is within the conical zone and the value reduces when the bed height reaches at the upper cylindrical zone. The value of α almost linearly decreases with H_0 and d_p , whereas it increases with ρ_p .

The exponents over the parameters have been calculated based on the experimental values, and they are essentially the slopes of the lines relating the natural log of dependent and independent variables. Functional dependency of α on H_0 , ρ_p & d_p has been analysed and found the following:

- $\alpha = f(H_0^{-2.28}, \rho_p^{3.75}, d_p^{-9.30})$ when $H_0 < H_c$
- $\alpha = f(H_0^{-1.87}, \rho_p^{2.75}, d_p^{-3.78})$ when $H_0 > H_c$

However, in general, one can assume the value of α in the following manner for a quick calculation of u_{ms} .

- Within the conical zone, α may be assumed as:
 - 1.5 for $\rho_p > 6 \text{ g/cc}$ and $d_p < 1 \text{ mm}$.
 - 1.0 for $2 < \rho_p < 6 \text{ g/cc}$ and $1 < d_p < 2.5 \text{ mm}$.
 - 0.5 for $\rho_p < 2 \text{ g/cc}$ and $d_p > 2.5 \text{ mm}$.
- Above the conical zone, α may be assumed as:
 - 1.0 for $\rho_p > 6 \text{ g/cc}$ and $d_p < 1 \text{ mm}$.
 - 0.5 for $\rho_p < 6 \text{ g/cc}$ and $d_p > 1 \text{ mm}$.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maider Bolaños: Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Idoia Estiati:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Palash Kumar Mollick:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mikel Tellabide:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Martin Olazar:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Xabier Sukunza:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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